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Corrigenda to the checklist of the Collembola (Hexapoda) of Belarus

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Abstract. Comments and corrections are provided for the checklist of Collembola of Belarus published previously, in which some records of families and genera were misplaced. Additionally, an error was noticed in the reference to *Isotomurus maculatus* (Schäffer, 1896), which should instead refer to *Orchesella bifasciata* Nicolet, 1842. Currently, according to the literary sources, four orders, 17 families, 55 genera and 113 species are registered in Belarus.

Key words: Collembola, checklist, *Orchesella bifasciata*, *Isotomurus maculatus*, Belarus.

Исправления к списку Collembola (Hexapoda) Беларуси

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Резюме. Даны комментарии и исправления к чек-листу коллембол Беларуси, опубликованному ранее, в котором были приведены некоторые некорректные сведения по семействам и родам. Была также замечена ошибка в ссылке на *Isotomurus maculatus* (Schäffer, 1896), которая вместо этого должна относиться к *Orchesella bifasciata* Nicolet, 1842. В настоящее время, согласно литературным источникам, в Беларуси зарегистрировано 4 отряда, 17 семейств, 55 родов и 113 видов.

Ключевые слова: ногохвостки, список видов, *Orchesella bifasciata*, *Isotomurus maculatus*, Беларусь.

The article dedicated to the history of Collembola research and the checklist of springtails of Belarus [Sinchuk et al., 2023] contains several inaccuracies concerning the current systematic classification of certain taxa [Janssens, Christiansen, 2011; Bellinger et al., 1996–2024].

The representative of the genus *Seira* Lubbock, 1870, *S. squamoornata* (Scherbakov, 1898), belongs to the family Entomobryidae, not to Hypogastruridae. All collembolan taxa of Isotomidae family belong to Entomobryomorpha order, instead of Poduromorpha. Representatives of the genera *Allacma* Börner, 1906, *Capraïnea* Dallai, 1970, *Lipothrix* Börner, 1906, *Sminthurus* Latreille, 1802 and *Spatulosminthurus* Betsch et Betsch-Pinot, 1983 must be classified within the family Sminthuridae, not Sminthurididae. The genus *Xenyllodes* Axelson, 1903 with its representative *X. armatus* Axelson, 1903 belongs to the family Odontellidae, not Onychiuridae.

The reference to *Isotomurus maculatus* (Schäffer, 1896) mentioned by Sinchuk et al. [2023] should instead refer to *Orchesella bifasciata* Nicolet, 1842. In addition, all citations of this species listed in Sinchuk et al. [2023] are wrong.

Notice also that the references to “Bourlet, 1839” [Bourlet, 1839] in the citations of Buşmachiu [2010] and of Borodin and Tsinkevich [2016] are incorrect and should have been referring to “Nicolet, 1842” [Nicolet, 1842].

Orchesella bifasciata Nicolet, 1842

Orchesella bifasciata Nicolet, 1842: Stach, 1960: 108.

Orchesella bifasciata: Kuznetsova, 1984: 257; Borodin, Krasouski, 2020.

Orchesella bifasciata (Nicolet, 1841 (sic)): Kuznetsova, 1988: 40.

Orchesella bifasciata Nic.: Sterzyńska, Kuznetsova, 1995: 149.

Orchesella bifasciata Bourlet, 1839 (sic): Buşmachiu, 2010: 119–121.

Orchesella bifasciata (Bourlet, 1839 (sic)): Borodin, Tsinkevich, 2016: 14.

In Buşmachiu [2010], the authority “Bourlet, 1839” is incorrect. It appears that Buşmachiu was actually referring to Stach [1960], who in turn cited *Orchesella bifasciata* Nicolet, 1842.

“*Orchesella bifasciata* (Bourlet, 1839)” sensu Borodin and Tsinkevich [2016: 14] is a lapsus for “*Orchesella bifasciata* Nicolet, 1842” (compared with Sterzyńska and Kuznetsova [1995] and Buşmachiu [2010]).

After the systematic and taxonomic revisions, the most biodiverse order in Belarus is Entomobryomorpha. In general, four orders, 17 families, 55 genera, and 113 species of Collembola are documented for the country (Figs 1, 2).

At present, the estimated diversity of Collembola in Belarus is 47.9% of possibly identified species, eight species require confirmation [Sinchuk et al., 2023]. More than 125 species of springtails are yet to be discovered [Ulrich, Fiera, 2009].

Figs 1–2. Taxonomic structure of springtails of Belarus.

1 – orders; 2 – families.

Рис. 1–2. Таксономическая структура ногохвосток Беларуси.

1 – отряды; 2 – семейства.

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